

Information Needs of Deaf Welders: Improving the Accessibility of Middle-Skill Work

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ABSTRACT

Past research on accessibility and usability has primarily focused on digital accessibility but has paid less attention to how middle-skill jobs could be made more accessible. While accessibility is still an important issue in many sectors, accessibility in middle skill jobs is particularly important given the disproportionate number of Deaf workers in manual labor jobs. Due to language deprivation and discrimination, Deaf workers face limited employment opportunities. However, welding can provide uniquely rewarding job opportunities for Deaf workers because of its visual and spatial nature. This research study examines accessibility in the welding industry and asks how Deaf welders experience welding training and work and how technology and training can be made more accessible. In this research, we take a participatory and user-centered design approach to understand the experiences and needs of Deaf welders. As a team of Deaf and hearing researchers, we conducted in-depth interviews with four Deaf welders. Our findings point to the need for accessible training resources and improvements to welding technology. Overall, our research sheds light on the everyday training and employment experiences of Deaf welders and highlights how advances in technology could benefit Deaf and hard of hearing welders.

KEYWORDS

Deaf workers; welding; user-centered design; accessibility; usability

INTRODUCTION

Dating back to the 1930s, middle-skill jobs have been envisioned as a promising career choice for Deaf people (Anderson, 1935). Accessibility in middle-skill jobs is particularly important given the overrepresentation of Deaf workers in industries such as welding. From an early age, many Deaf children face communication barriers, especially if their parents are not fluent in American Sign Language (ASL). Given that the first few years of life are critical for language acquisition, some Deaf children may not have enough opportunities to learn ASL or written English. As a result, many Deaf people experience language deprivation, which can have lifelong effects (Hall et al., 2017). Language deprivation can lead to Deaf people having difficulty finding jobs, resulting in underemployment and pay inequities (Garberoglio et al., 2019). However, due to its visual and manual nature, welding may provide uniquely rewarding job opportunities to Deaf workers.

Throughout history, society has viewed Deafness as a medical issue rather than a social issue (Stokoe, 2005). However, for the past several decades, the disabled and Deaf community have been advocating for the social model of disability which frames disability as a "socially and culturally constructed form of oppression" (Ellcessor, 2010, p. 292). This model emphasizes the barriers that society creates for disabled individuals (Stokoe, 2005). Disability rights activists argue that if society was constructed in a manner that is accessible for individuals with disabilities, these individuals would not be considered disabled. Ultimately, rather than disabilities being a medical condition, the social model of disability views disabilities such as Deafness as conditions forced on the disabled due to societal failure to provide accessible environments. Based on the social model of disability, many Deaf people consider deafness as a culture of people with their own history, language, and values (Young & Ackerman, 2001). As such, many Deaf people prefer to capitalize the word "Deaf" as opposed to "deaf" to signify that they are a community with a unique language and culture (Pudans-Smith et al., 2019). Because Deaf people see deafness as an important part of their identity, many prefer to use identity-first language (e.g., Deaf people) rather than people-first language (e.g., people who are Deaf) (Smith & Samar, 2016). Thus, in this paper, we capitalize "Deaf" and use identity-first language throughout.

Although there is a growing body of research on accessibility and usability, this literature has focused primarily on digital accessibility but has paid less attention to how middle-skill jobs or associated training and technology could be made more accessible (Saur et al., 2020). Middle-skill jobs are those that require more education than a high school degree, but less than a four-year college degree (Holzer & Lehrman, 2007). Examples of middle-skill jobs include electricians, technicians, and welders. The demand for middle-skill jobs is high and growing relative to the supply of middle-skill workers.

Further, Deaf communities are disproportionately understudied (Mack et al., 2021; Stokoe, 2005). But research on usability, accessibility, and design argues that paying attention to the user experience of special populations can lead to more universally accessible design that also benefits other users (Saur et al., 2020; Wobbrock et al., 2011). Based on this line of reasoning, understanding the user experiences of Deaf welders may reveal design needs that benefit all welders.

Thus, this study focuses on understanding the experiences and needs of Deaf welders. We ask: What are the challenges and benefits that Deaf welders experience in welding? What innovations can make welding technology and training more accessible to Deaf welders? In this research, we take a participatory and user-centered design approach to understand the experiences and needs of Deaf welders. We conducted interviews with four Deaf welders and found that welding careers can be rewarding for Deaf people, that there is a lack of accessible education for Deaf welders, that Deaf people must navigate prejudice and discrimination in hiring and employment, and that there are potential improvements in welding technology and training that can make them more accessible for Deaf and hearing welders. Overall, our research sheds light on the everyday training and employment experiences of Deaf welders and highlights advantages and disadvantages of being a Deaf or hard of hearing welder.

BACKGROUND

Language deprivation and resulting lower literacy levels can lead to limited job opportunities for Deaf workers. Due to their visual and manual nature, middle-skill jobs provide job opportunities to many Deaf workers. Deaf workers are more likely than hearing workers to end up in middle-skill jobs compared to white-collar jobs (Anderson et al., 2018; Luft, 2000; Schroedel & Geyer, 2000). Nearly 90% of Deaf workers work in manual labor compared to 50% of hearing workers (Luft, 2000). Similarly, a study on Deaf high school students' vocational interests and attitudes found that Deaf students were more interested than hearing students in middle-skill jobs like machine operation and mechanics (Farrugia, 1982).

Deaf workers also experience limited job opportunities due to the prejudice and discrimination that Deaf welders may face in seeking jobs and sustaining their careers. Though the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) made discrimination against Deaf people illegal in theory, in practice Deaf workers still face discrimination in their workplace and resistance from employers in providing accommodations required by law (Bowe et al., 2005). For example, many employers believe that Deaf workers are less able to advance in their careers (Luft, 2000). Deaf workers are often the first to be laid off from companies with primarily hearing workers (Morris, 2019). Studies on the employment of Deaf workers reveal different strategies for navigating such prejudices in job seeking and employment. Some Deaf workers do not reveal their Deafness while other Deaf workers try to overachieve (Lindsay, 2020). Other Deaf workers have given up on finding traditional jobs and, instead, are starting their own businesses (Morris, 2019), where they prefer to hire Deaf workers (Lindsay, 2020).

Although there is a growing body of research on accessibility and usability, there is a lack of research on accessibility in middle-skill jobs (Saur et al., 2020). The need for research on middle-skill jobs is particularly stark given the large overrepresentation of Deaf welders in these industries (Luft, 2000). This study helps fill this gap in research by understanding the experiences and needs of Deaf welders.

METHODS

This research takes a participatory and user-centered design approach to understand the experiences and needs of Deaf welders. This research is based on in-depth semi-structured interviews conducted with four Deaf welders in Austin, Texas during the summer of 2022. We used snowball sampling to recruit Deaf welders for our interviews. Interview participants were compensated with a US \$40 Target gift card. This research was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Review Board of the University of Texas at Austin. Each interview was conducted in person in a public location (college campuses and coffee shops) and lasted about one hour. Interviews were audio-recorded and were transcribed using Otter.ai. Transcribed interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Researchers coded the interview transcripts separately and then compared thematic codes to see which themes were consistently common. The results presented in this paper represent the consensus across multiple independent coders.

Our team consisted of Deaf and hearing researchers. All interviews were conducted with the assistance of paid ASL interpreters. During all interviews, the first author, who is hearing, was the primary interviewer and asked questions in spoken English while the interpreter signed in ASL. The third author, who is Deaf, also asked questions in ASL during the interview. These questions were interpreted for the hearing researchers present during the interview. Research participants varied in their need for interpretation. Two participants used interpretation to understand and to respond to questions. One participant used a hearing aid and interpretation to understand questions and respond to questions in spoken English. Another participant used an interpreter to understand questions and responded to questions with simultaneous communication (SimCom), a technique that uses spoken language and signing simultaneously.

From the perspective of nothing about us without us (Charlton, 1998), having a Deaf person, and specifically a Deaf welder, on our team made us particularly well-suited to conduct this research. The third author's identity as a member of the Deaf community contributed to building rapport with research participants during the recruitment process and the interviews. She also was a source of expertise on both Deaf culture and welding. Her helpful input allowed us to hone our interview questions and gain unique insights into the experiences of Deaf welders. She also helped review interview transcripts to ensure that the interpreters interpreted the interview accurately and corrected words that have the same or similar sign in ASL.

The research participants had different levels of experience and expertise in welding and welding training. Participant 1 was a White woman and undergraduate student taking welding classes at a local community college and participated in welding projects at a local university. Participant 2 was a White man who had created and taught in multiple welding programs for Deaf students. Participant 3 was a Latino man, who primarily worked as contract welder at various worksites including laying pipelines. Participant 4 was a White man and a welder who had worked in various welding jobs including the oil and gas industry.

RESULTS

Due to the spatial nature of welding, Deaf people may be well-suited to a career in welding; however, Deaf welders still experience inaccessibility in welding technology and training. Many Deaf welders have developed their own ways to learn how to weld and use welding technology without relying on hearing. For example, while many hearing welders monitor the sound of the weld to distinguish a good weld from a bad weld, Deaf welders may not be able to rely on the sound of a weld to know if their weld is good. Participant 2 explained, "A lot of people say, listen to the sound of bacon. And if you hear bacon, you're doing the weld right." Instead of relying on sound, Deaf welders may focus on visual and physical cues. For example, when learning how to set the correct oxygen and acetylene mixtures for the acetylene cutting torch, Participant 1 was trained to pay close attention to the flame and smoke rather than monitoring the sound. She said, "I thought that was a standardized thing. And then it wasn't until much later they said, 'No, no, go by the sound.'" She continued, "It never occurred to me to listen to different sounds." Participant 4 explained that he uses physical sensations while welding. When he feels a "frying" sensation that feels like cooking bacon, it means that he has a proper arc length. Arc length is when the electrode touches the metal, it creates an arc where the filler metal of the electrode makes a deposit to the main metal. If a welder goes too far away from the metal, it will get dirty, splattery, and smoky. You can feel irregular popping of the filler going crazy because the arc is going all over place. Participant 1 also noted that Deaf welders can feel the heat of metal to determine if the metal is overheated. Participant 3 explained that to ensure that he is welding at the right pace, he watches how the "lava" puddle shapes when the electrode touches and melts the main metal. He explained that if the puddle is oval, the welder is moving too fast. The objective is to make a perfect circle of puddle.

Visual metrics indicating whether a weld has the "right" sound may be helpful for training new welders, including Deaf welders. For example, Participant 1 suggested improving welding technology with sensors for correct oxygen and acetylene mixtures. She explained, "If I get the mixture, right, the green light pops on, you know what I mean? Because everybody else can depend on the hearing of the mixture. I just didn't. I mean, it's a visual – to see the flame." Participant 1 noted that having an indicator for accurate gas mixtures could help Deaf and new welders learn how to set the mixtures faster and improve the weld. However, Participant 1 also noted that developing an indicator for gas mixtures might not be an easy task. She noted that there are a lot of variables including thickness of the metal, temperature, torch position, as well as other factors. Participant 3 also had suggestions for visual indicators. Participant 3 wanted "something that senses range or tells you to slow down something like that... something that you can see if something's too hot and it's flashing an alarm at you. That's not necessarily related to just being Deaf, but that could work for anyone." As noted by Participant 3, visual indicators could make welding more accessible to all welders, not just to Deaf welders.

As VR technology has developed, there has been more adoption of auditory cues over visual cues. Participant 2 mentioned that in the early stages, VR technology was more visual and Deaf-friendly since there were visual indicators on the screen. He noted that current VR technology is focused on making the VR screen in the hood appear more realistic, resulting in fewer visual indicators and making the technology less accessible for Deaf welders. Participant 2 expressed that VR technology would be a game changer to teach Deaf people how to weld since they could make sounds visible. Participant 2 also expressed frustration with being unable to verbally instruct Deaf welding students while they are welding. Hearing students can listen to their instructor comment on their weld, while they are welding. For Deaf welders, instructors must disrupt the welder's practice to explain their errors. Thus, Participant 2 believed that VR technology could offer a way for Deaf students to practice welding and get visual cues from VR technology without disruptions. He also noted that VR technology could have profound impacts on encouraging younger Deaf people to weld as there are no safety risks with VR welding.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Our research reveals that improvements to welding technology and training could improve training and work experiences for Deaf welders and new welders in general. Augmenting welding technology with visual metrics of sound, heat, and other indicators of a good weld could improve welding training for Deaf welders and hearing welders alike. Overall, our research sheds light on the training and employment experiences of Deaf welders and highlights advantages and disadvantages of being a Deaf or hard of hearing welder. Ultimately, based on the results of our study, we conclude that 1) as a visual field of work, welding may be a particularly advantageous career for Deaf workers; and 2) that Deaf-accessible welding training and technology is needed to help provide Deaf welders with the skills to be successful in welding.

Our study contributes to the growing conversation on accessibility, work, and technology. Our research also points to the importance of making welding training resources more accessible to Deaf populations. Finally, there is a need for more research in the information field providing guidance on how best to conduct research with Deaf people (Anderson et al, 2018; Ferndale, 2018; McKee et al., 2013; Stone & West, 2012; Wilson & Winiarczyk, 2014; Wolsey et al., 2017). Our research provides methodological insights into conducting research with Deaf people. We conclude that Deaf researchers offer unique expertise and that their involvement can lead to richer data and research results than hearing-only research teams.

Our research provided rich information on the working lives of Deaf welders; however, our study is not without limitations. Since we were only able to conduct four interviews, we cannot be assured that our findings are generalizable to all Deaf welders. Additionally, all our research participants were from a specific geographical location. Future research should recruit a larger sample of Deaf welders from across the United States, including rural areas where there may be decreased access to interpreters or less competition for Deaf welders in finding jobs.

Our research brings up questions that require future research. Further research is needed to understand the extent of disadvantage that Deaf workers experience in hiring, wages, performance evaluations, and other important aspects of work. Many of our research participants noted that employers cited safety concerns as a reason not to hire or retain Deaf welders. Thus, future research should examine whether Deaf welders are at increased risk of injury. Additionally, our research brings up further questions on how welding technology and training could be improved to meet the information needs of new and Deaf welders. For example, could welding equipment be augmented with sensors that allow for visual indications of sound? More research is needed to fill the gaps in knowledge on how to meet the information needs of Deaf people. There is a need for more research within the information field about how to best serve Deaf people using new information technologies and services.

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